

Preliminary investigations into drift capture efficiency of off-field plant canopies

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Summary

To determine pesticide spray drift exposure of non-target organisms for the risk assessment, drift deposition to horizontal collectors like petri dishes is currently used. There is little information about the volume of airborne drift captured by vertical, 3-D off-crop structures, such as plants. Preliminary wind tunnel investigations indicated that rows of plants capture similar volumes as single plants but that blocks of plants differ in the quantity captured. The front row of plants in a block, unsurprisingly, captures the most spray drift while a few rows back, the amount captured falls off considerably. There are also differences in spray drift capture depending on plant species. The results support the assumption that the standard regulatory spray drift exposure estimations based on horizontal collection do not reflect the reality of spray drift capture by off-crop canopies. Development of new testing and modelling based approaches would allow for a more realistic risk assessment.

Key words: Spray drift; exposure; canopy; capture efficiency, non-target plants; plant protection product; risk assessment

Introduction

Considering the European regulatory context, non-target terrestrial plants (NTTPs) are, by definition, located outside of the area treated with plant protection products (PPP), generally referred to as the off-field (EFSA, 2022). Accordingly, they can be unintentionally exposed to PPPs via drift, which is considered to be the main exposure route for NTTPs and therefore taken into account for the risk assessment. The extent to which NTTPs are expected to be exposed to drift in the off-field is defined by the Rautmann drift value tables (Rautmann, 2001). For example, for an application to field crops with a standard nozzle (no drift reduction), an exposure of 2.77% of the rate applied in the field is expected in the first metre next to the field/application area. These expectations represent the 90th percentile of drift and are based on a data set generated in field drift studies using horizontal ground collectors like petri dishes. Drift deposition to flat collectors is considered a reasonable surrogate for determining spray drift loadings to water bodies. However, plants have a third dimension and other characteristics that are variable e.g., canopy porosity, plant structure, width, depth, height, surface structure (hairy, smooth, waxy, etc.: Forster *et al.*, 2012). This raises the questions which of the characteristics of the off-field vegetation are most important for determining its drift capture

efficiency and how to take capture efficiency into considerations when drift values for regulatory purposes are estimated as recently discussed in an EFSA-supported publication (Adriaanse *et al.*, 2022).

There is currently very little information about the spray drift capture efficiency of off-field structures such as plants. Capture efficiency of an object is defined by Spillman, (1984) as the ratio of the volume of droplets caught to the volume of droplets that would have passed through the cross-sectional area of the object during the time of exposure, had the obstacle not been there. Accordingly, in order to determine the drift capture efficiency of a plant or a canopy of plants, the volume of airborne spray deposited on the plants/canopy and the dimensions/cross-sectional area of the collecting object(s) are the factors that need to be considered (May & Clifford, 1967). The volume of airborne spray drift to which NTTPs are exposed can be determined through field experiments, wind tunnel experiments or modelling. A number of spray drift models exist (e.g. Butler Ellis & Miller, 2010; Casanova *et al.*, 2022) that can predict the quantity of airborne spray at regulatory relevant distances in the off-crop, e.g. 1, 2, 3, 5, 10 m next to the treated area. A further modelling step is needed that ideally takes deposition on the plants as well as the plants' dimensions into account to determine how much of the airborne spray is captured. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has been proposed as a route to achieving this (Dunne *et al.*, 2023) as this method is capable of including 3D characteristics of the plants into the equation. However, experimental data is lacking that would be needed to inform spray drift models and CFD.

As a first attempt, a method was developed to experimentally investigate quantity of spray drift deposits on plants under controlled conditions in a wind tunnel. To get first insights into the possible influence that the characteristics of the off-field vegetation have on drift capture efficiency, drift deposition on four species representing different growth types and 3D structures was investigated with the plants arranged as single plants, rows (1 × 5 potted plants) and blocks (5 × 5 rows), respectively, to account for different dimensions in the off-crop.

Materials and Methods

Plant species and collectors investigated

Four different plant species, grown as single plants in pots, were selected to represent different growth forms and surface structures (Fig. 1). Soy (*Glycine max*) was chosen to represent smaller plant species with broad leaves and little hair, used at BBCH 23-29, during side shoot development. Oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*) represents plants with a medium height and medium sized leaves building a waxy cuticula, used at BBCH 30-35. For tall, plants with broad leaves and a hairy surface, sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) was used at BBCH 32–36 where the plants are still in a rosette-stadium and stem elongation had not yet set in. Representing grassy plants with long, thin leaves, oats (*Avena sativa*) was used at BBCH 30–35 after tillering. In addition, stainless-steel steel rods of 2 mm diameter as upright collectors were used to be able to compare between experimental runs based on a standardized collector.

Experimental set-up (Fig. 1)

Experiments were conducted at two wind speeds (1 m s⁻¹ and 2 m s⁻¹) and with a pair of nozzles (F110-03) at 3 bar pressure under controlled conditions in a wind tunnel. As 2 m s⁻¹ is a relatively high wind speed when extrapolated from the wind tunnel to the outside world, this wind speed was chosen for the row and block experiment to represent a worst-case situation. The boom was driven across the wind tunnel at 0.6 m height at 10 km h⁻¹ delivering approximately 142 L ha⁻¹ under the boom. Four or 10 passes of the spray boom were done per

experiment to ensure enough deposition/capture for reliable measurements. Three replicates of each set-up and plant type, respectively, were conducted. Plants grown in pots were placed in the wind tunnel to determine the drift deposit and an array of 2 mm diameter stainless-steel rods were placed alongside to measure the quantity of airborne spray at the same location. Single plants were placed at three distances downwind (1, 3 and 5 m) at two wind speeds (1 m s⁻¹ and 2 m s⁻¹). Rows of five plants and blocks of 5 × 5 plants were centred at 3 m down-wind to avoid the potential for overspray which may occur at 1 m.

Fig. 1. Collectors and experimental set-up of the wind tunnel experiments. Four plant species (soy (*Glycine max*), oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*), sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*), oats (*Avena sativa*)), representing four different growth and structure types were used together with stainless steel rods as collectors. Three different experimental set-ups (Single plants, Row and Block) were used to determine capture efficiency of the collectors.

“Green S” dye and colorimetry immediately after application were used for analysis. Deposit on plants was expressed as μL tank mix per g plant fresh weight. Plant mean weights were sunflower 57.7 g plant⁻¹, oilseed rape 54.4 g plant⁻¹, soy 23.4 g plant⁻¹, and oats 35.7 g plant⁻¹. Airborne spray concentration is derived from the quantity deposited on rods per unit cross-

sectional area. For oats, oilseed rape and sunflower (larger plants), all horizontal collectors of the steel rods were used to determine the airborne spray concentration. For comparing to soy as a smaller plant, only the lower eight horizontal rods were used.

Results

To ensure the reliability and reproducibility of the wind tunnel regarding generated drift, the amounts of spray liquid captured by steel rods in $\mu\text{L m}^2$ equalling airborne spray at a certain distance from the boom were compared (data not shown). Generally, the data confirms that the plants were exposed to approximately the same drift amount across all experiments with the arrangement of the plants potentially affecting capture efficiency of the rods which may eventually be due to edge effects. Nevertheless, to be able to compare between experiments where the drifted volume may change, it is important to relate the measured deposits on plants to the quantity in the air that they were exposed to. Even small, statistically insignificant changes in the quantity in the air, as they were recorded in our experiments, will potentially lead to changes in the deposits.

Single oat, soy, oilseed rape and sunflower plants were placed at three distances downwind (1, 3 and 5 m) at two wind speeds (1 m s^{-1} and 2 m s^{-1}) (Fig. 1). Comparisons of the amounts of spray liquid captured by steel rods in $\mu\text{L m}^2$ equalling airborne spray at a certain distance from the boom revealed that lot of drift was captured at 1 m distance with a rapid decline with distance (approximately 7-fold at 3 m, 25-fold at 5 m) as shown in Fig. 2 for the example of oilseed rape plants.

Fig. 2. Correlation between airborne spray and deposits on single oilseed rape plants at 1, 3 or 5 m down-wind of spray boom at 1 or 2 m s^{-1} wind speed.

The deposition on the single plants differed according to the tested species with soy, oats and oilseed rape collecting similar quantities of spray and sunflower collecting the lowest amount (Fig. 3A). For oats and oilseed rape, a second run of the experiment was conducted using an upwind baffle in the wind tunnel to create a logarithmic wind profile with the same wind speed as in the first run around the nozzle but a lower wind speed at 3 m down-wind where the plants are located. While deposits on oilseed rape plants was similar in both runs (Fig. 3C), oat plants were catching more airborne spray in the second run (Fig. 3B).

Fig. 3. Correlation between airborne spray and deposits on plants for four species (soy, oilseed rape, sunflower, oats) arranged as single plants at 3 m down-wind of spray boom at 2 m s⁻¹ wind speed. A) Results of the first run conducted in the standard wind tunnel set-up. B) and C) In a second run, oats and oilseed rape were tested with an upwind baffle in the wind tunnel to create a logarithmic wind profile with the same wind speed as in the first run around the nozzle but a lower wind speed at 3 m down-wind where the plants are located. Data of the first run (red) and the second run with the modified setting (blue) are shown in comparison.

Approximately the same airborne spray g⁻¹ fresh weight was deposited on single plants as on rows of plant for all species, with the exception of sunflower. Rows of sunflower plants captured only half as much as the single plants (data not shown). At the front row of a block of

5 × 5 plants, as shown in Fig 4, the measured amounts of μL deposit g^{-1} fresh weight were similar or even higher than for single plants and rows of plants for all species.

Fig. 4. Deposit on plants for four species (soy, oilseed rape, sunflower, oats) arranged in blocks of 5 × 5 plants at 3 m down-wind of the spray boom at 2 m s^{-1} wind speed. One column represents deposited $\mu\text{L g}^{-1}$ fresh weight for one plant.

It has to be considered, that the front row of a block was located at around 2.5 m down-wind while the rows and single plants were located 3 m down-wind, which explains the higher amounts measured. Unsurprisingly, the middle of a block (3rd row) had much less deposit of airborne spray g⁻¹ fresh weight than single plants, rows or the front of a block (Fig. 4). Depending on the species, the capture efficiency of plants was reduced approximately by a factor of 2–5 when they were placed in the middle of the blocks.

Discussion

This preliminary investigation of the deposits of spray on four different plant species in a wind tunnel confirmed that capture efficiency of plants depends on the species, having size, shape or structure of the plant as one of the main factors influencing how much of the airborne drift is captured. Looking at the pictures of the tested plants, sunflowers, growing comparably thin stems and few, horizontal but large leaves, seem to be the logical species to collect the least of the airborne spray out of all four species tested. At the same time, sunflower is a relatively heavy plant with a low surface to weight ratio. Presented results were recorded in μL spray solution/g fresh weight, therefore heavier plants will appear to capture less spray drift. It has to be discussed what would be a better reference figure to be able to directly assess capture efficiencies of plants which would allow for comparisons between experiments and species. Surface area or cross-sectional area are likely to be more relevant but time-consuming to measure.

May & Clifford, (1967) indicate that capture efficiency of 3D objects (in our case plants) does not only depend on their inherent qualities but changes with wind speed. Comparing deposits on oats and oilseed rape in two different wind profiles (first and second run) confirms this but also shows that the wind-profile-induced changes in deposition seem to be species dependent as deposition on oats changes with the wind profile while that on oilseed rape stays relatively constant. In addition, the movement of plants in an air current, also dependent on species and growth stage, will affect the collection efficiency. For example, thin, blade-shaped, upright leaves like grasses will move around more in stronger winds than large leaves of a rosette plant. Additional experiments at different wind speeds could show whether capture efficiency of a certain plant species and wind speed have different relationship with wind speed from a rigid structure (such as the rods). In addition, formulation type may also have an influence on capture efficiency of a plant as some adjuvants in PPPs may for example help droplets stick to hydrophobic, waxy leaf surfaces or penetrate through an otherwise protective layer of hair on the plant.

As plants normally grow in canopies next to agricultural fields, investigations of the relative effects of rows and small blocks of plants on the deposition of in-flight spray drift were conducted. The front row of plants, unsurprisingly, captures the most spray drift whereas just a few rows back, the amount of spray drift captured falls off considerably, even for a notably porous structure. The presented results indicate that plants growing in the canopy directly next to the field will catch the highest amount of drift but that just some centimetres inside the canopy, the captured drift is much lower. Neither these canopy effects nor the effects of plant species on off-crop drift capture are considered in the NTTTP risk assessment for PPPs which is based on Rautmann drift tables (2001). For the regulatory context, where drift is considered relative to the applied dose (i.e. in-field), an estimation of the capture efficiency as a percentage of the applied dose seems to be the next logical step. However, this is not possible for this data set as the quantity that would be deposited on the plant species when directly over-sprayed was not measured. Further wind tunnel experiments aiming to determine deposition on and capture

efficiency of NTTPs need to be appropriately set up to represent field conditions while recognising that wind tunnels often give higher absolute levels of airborne spray than in the field because of the lack of turbulence and dispersion. In addition, experiments under realistic conditions in the field measuring deposition on various plant species both under the boom and at several distances down-wind while also estimating plant capture efficiency by measuring surface or cross-sectional area of the exposed plants would allow for an allocation of exposure, in % of applied dose, that could be used for the NTTP risk assessment.

In summary, the results support the assumption that the standard exposure estimations based on horizontal collection of spray drift used in risk assessments do not reflect the reality of spray drift capture by off-crop canopies, confirming Dunne *et al.*, (2023) and Ariaansen *et al.*, (2022), in that the effect of PPP spray drift on (not only) NTTP adjacent to treated fields is currently dealt with in a very simplified way in the European regulatory system. Development of new testing and modelling based exposure estimation approaches would allow for a more realistic risk assessment approach but require a better understanding of the capture efficiency of NTTPs next to agricultural fields in Europe.

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